

REGULAR GENERALIZED FUNCTIONS
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ABSTRACT

In the theory of distributions, a regular generalized function is a functional that can be represented by a locally integrable function. For any test function in the space (smooth functions with compact support), the regular distribution is defined by the integral.

Definition. In the theory of distributions, a regular generalized function is a functional that can be represented by a locally integrable function $f(x) \in L^1_{loc}(G)$. For any test function $\varphi(x)$ in the space $D(G)$ (smooth functions with compact support), the regular distribution f is defined by the integral:

$$(f, \varphi) = \int_G f(x)\varphi(x)dx$$

A functional

$$(f, \varphi) = \int_G f(x)\varphi(x)dx \quad (1)$$

created using a function $f(x)$ that is locally integrable in the domain G serves as the simplest example of a generalized function (distribution) for any $\varphi \in D(G)$. The linearity of this functional follows from the linearity of the integral. Accordingly, the following equality is established:

$$\begin{aligned} (f, \lambda\varphi + \mu\psi) &= \int_G f(x)[\lambda\varphi(x) + \mu\psi(x)]dx = \\ &= \lambda \int_G f(x)\varphi(x)dx + \mu \int_G f(x)\psi(x)dx = \lambda (f, \varphi) + \mu (f, \psi). \end{aligned}$$

According to the theorem on passing to the limit under the integral sign, the continuity of this functional in the space $D(G)$ also follows; that is, if $\varphi_k \rightarrow 0$ in $D(G)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$, then as $k \rightarrow \infty$ for $G' \subset G$ it follows

$$(f, \varphi_k) = \int_{G'} f(x)\varphi_k(x)dx \rightarrow 0.$$

A generalized function (1) created using a function $f(x)$ that is locally integrable in the domain G is called a regular generalized function. Other generalized functions are called singular generalized functions.

Lemma 1. (Du Bois-Reymond). For a locally integrable function $f(x)$ in the domain G to vanish almost everywhere in that domain, it is necessary and sufficient that the generalized function $f(x)$ created by it vanishes in that domain G .

It follows from the Du Bois-Reymond lemma that for a function continuous in the domain G , the support of the function and the support of the generalized function it defines coincide.

If a sequence of functions $f_k(x)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots$ that are locally integrable in the domain G converges uniformly to a function $f(x)$ on every compact set $K \subset G$, then $f_k(x) \rightarrow f(x)$ in the space $D'(G)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

Let $f \in D'(G)$ and $G_1 \subset G$. If the generalized function $f \in D'(G)$ coincides with the function $f_1 \in C^k(G_1)$ in the domain G_1 - that is, if for any test function $\varphi \in D(G_1)$ the equality

$$(f, \varphi) = \int_G f_1(x) \varphi(x) dx$$

holds - then the generalized function f is said to belong to the class $C^k(G_1)$. If, in addition, $f_1 \in C^k(\overline{G_1})$, then the generalized function f is said to belong to the class $C^k(\overline{G_1})$.

Theorem 1. If a sequence of generalized functions $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k, \dots$ from the space D' is such that for any $\varphi \in D$, the numerical sequence (f_k, φ) converges as $k \rightarrow \infty$, then the functional defined for any $\varphi \in D$ in the space of test functions by the equality:

$$(f, \varphi) = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} (f_k, \varphi)$$

is also linear and continuous in the space of test functions; that is, $f \in D'$

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